

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Medical Students Regarding Vitamin D

Ruqqaya Juanid¹, Saadia Feroz¹, Aashi Mughal²

¹House Officers, RMU and Allied Hospitals

²Assistant Professor, HITEC Institute of Medical Sciences

Abstract

Background: Recent studies document inadequate awareness about vitamin D even among the doctors.

Objective: This research was organized to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of medical students who will be the future doctors then.

Methods: It is a descriptive cross-sectional type of study, which has been carried out from August 2017 to January 2018 on 340 medical students of Rawalpindi Medical University, selected through systematic random sampling. A valid questionnaire (D-KAP-38) was taken from a study conducted in Tehran was used which consisted of 38 questions. Section A and B of the questionnaire consisted of general and nutritional knowledge questions while section C and D consisted of questions regarding attitude and practice. SPSS version 23 was utilized for analyzing data. Statistical significance was determined using Chi square test.

Results: Male and female participants were almost equal. Majority (57%) belonged to the age group 21-23 years. Moreover, majority (44%) had per month family income Rs. 50,000 to 1 lac. About 54% students had good general knowledge with greater proportion (65.6%) in age group 24 years ($p=0.7$). About 47% students had good nutritional knowledge with higher percentage in males than females ($p=0.01$). About 33% participants had good attitude with higher proportion in females than males ($p=0.01$). Only 8.8% students had good practice with females being more practicing ($p=0.00$).

Conclusion: Findings show average knowledge and attitude and poor practice. This is quite alarming considering the fact that study population consists of medical students.

Key Words: Vitamin D, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Sun exposure.

Introduction

Vitamin D, the sunshine vitamin, is the most readily available vitamin which is essential for calcium homeostasis and bone health¹. It is interestingly the most readily available and the most deficient vitamin at the same time². It is estimated that about 1 billion suffer from hypovitaminosis globally and the major burden falls in South-East Asia^{3, 4}. Medical literature documents hypovitaminosis D in all age groups and both genders in South-East Asian population so much so that it has been stated as unrecognized epidemic in many researches³. The advancement in medical research has revealed new dimensions of consequences of vitamin D deficiency linking it to many chronic diseases like Cancer, Heart Diseases, Diabetes type 1 and 2 and many other diseases^{4,5}. A national study has reported high levels of vitamin D deficiency in all age groups and both genders with 53.5% being vitamin D deficient and 31.2% being vitamin D insufficient⁶.

According to a KAP survey done in Australia 30% participants did not have any knowledge of vitamin D⁷. Among those who had some knowledge, 18% were not aware about its role in bone health while 40% mentioned the benefits that are to be confirmed yet. About 50% participants mentioned that in order to be vitamin D sufficient in summer, we need over 10 minutes of sunlight and 28% thought that this time should be increased to over 20 minutes in winter. Participants (11%) who believed that protection from sun makes one to be deficient in vitamin D, were less frequent users of sunscreens. As per a KAP survey conducted in female students in Saudi Arabia, students had inadequate knowledge and insufficient exposure to sun because of geographical, cultural and religious factors⁸.

A national level study was conducted at Karachi to know about vitamin D-related-knowledge among doctors showed results which concluded that doctors should enhance their knowledge and skills,

particularly in diagnosing and managing hypovitaminosis D⁹. A study done on medical students of Islamabad Medical and Dental College showed that most participants (99%) were well acquainted with the vital functions of this vitamin in human body but 84.5% had no idea about its recommended dietary allowance¹⁰.

Sunlight vitamin as the name shows has sun as its major source and thus individuals who are not mobile enough like patients or geriatric population should be the only victims of hypovitaminosis. But this is not the case as evident by previous studies¹⁰. Thus, such studies provoked the idea that hypovitaminosis D seems somewhat logical in geriatric population but 'why in young adults' is a question that still needs to be explored¹¹. Moreover, if doctors are inadequate in their knowledge about vitamin D deficiency then definitely adequacy of knowledge should also be assessed at the level of medical students. Thus, this research was organized to evaluate the knowledge together with attitude and practice towards vitamin D of this segment of population.

Main aim of the study was to determine the level of the knowledge, attitude as well as practice of MBBS (Bachelors of Medicine Bachelors of Surgery) students regarding vitamin D. Moreover, another aim was to compare the results with their gender, age, academic year and family income.

Materials and Methods

This is a cross-sectional descriptive type of study that included 340 medical students with equal participation through first year to final year. Sample size calculated using WHO sample size calculator, keeping the confidence interval 95% and considering the study "Evaluation of Knowledge, Practices of Vitamin D and Attitude Toward Sunlight Among Indian Students' as a reference with 53.3% as estimated percentage used from this reference study. This study was carried out from month of August to October 2017 in Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi. Participants were selected using systematic random method of sampling. A developed, valid & reliable questionnaire (D-KAP-38) was distributed among the participants to collect the required data. D-KAP-38 was developed by Parisa et al who conducted their study in Tehran¹² to develop a valid and reliable questionnaire and encouraged its use by other researchers. The questionnaire consisted of 38 questions which were subdivided into four

sections. Section A and B consisted of questions relevant to general knowledge (about vitamin D requirements of each gender, different age groups, pregnancy and form of sun exposure required) and nutritional knowledge (about food sources) respectively. While section C and D consisted of questions about attitude and practice respectively (Table 1).

Attitude	
17	Urbanization prevents sun exposure and production of required vitamin D.
18	A shortage of public places for outdoor activities prevents the sun exposure required for production of vitamin D
19	Full time indoor occupation prevents the sun exposure required for production of vitamin D.
20	Inefficient education regarding benefits of sun exposure prevents production of required vitamin D through sun exposure.
21	The undesirable taste of sea foods is one of the barriers to consumption of dietary sources.
22	In vitamin D deficiency, supplement intake is more effective compared to dietary intake and sun exposure.
23	Taking vitamin D supplement, unless recommended by physicians is wrong.
24	Unwillingness of individuals to take vitamin D supplement is one of the barriers of providing this nutrient.
25	Taking supplements is necessary for treatment of vitamin D deficiency but not for its prevention.
26	Permanent using of sunscreens on face, neck and hands prevents the sun exposure required for production of vitamin D.
27	Taking supplement is only necessary in case of lack of exposure to sunlight.
28	A high expense of dietary sources of vitamin D is one of the barriers of providing this nutrient.
Practice	
29	For sufficient exposure to sunlight I regularly engage in outdoor physical activities.
30	To be vitamin D sufficient, I consume fortified milk.
31	In order to be vitamin D sufficient, I consume fish at least twice a week.
32	For sufficient exposure to sunlight I walk outdoors daily.
33	I use caps/hats to avoid severe sun exposure.
34	To be vitamin D sufficient, I take vitamin D supplements.
35	I use sunscreen on my hands.
36	During the day I am directly exposed to sunlight (outdoors).
37	During the day I am indirectly exposed to sunlight (through glass).
38	I use sunscreen on my face.

Table I: Section C and D of Questionnaire (D-KAP-38)

In section A the possible responses (Yes/No/I don't know) were scored as 2/0/1 respectively. Likewise, in section B scoring was similar to section A except for question 12(Fatty fishes are one of the main dietary sources of vitamin D) which was inversely scored as 2/0/1. In section

C of questionnaire, the possible responses of “strongly disagree to strongly agree” were rated on a 5 Likert scale with the allocated scores of 1 to 5 respectively. Lastly, section D with possible responses as “never/ rarely/ sometimes/ often/ always” was rated similarly such that the scores of 1 to 5 were allocated to the responses of questions 29, 30, 31, 32, 34 and 36 and other questions were scored inversely. In general knowledge maximum score was 32 and it was divided as 0-11, 12-21 and 22-32 respectively. Similarly, for nutritional knowledge score was divided as 0-3, 4-6 and 7-10. For Attitude score was divided as 0-19, 20-39 and 40-60 respectively. Lastly, in ‘Practice section’ maximum score was divided as 0-16, 17-33, and 34-50 respectively. Finally, total score of each participant was calculated and categorized accordingly as having good/average/poor in terms of all four parameter. Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS) version 23 was used for analyzing the data. For qualitative variables (gender, age groups, year of study and socio-economic status) percentages and frequencies were calculated. Using Chi square test, it was determined whether a particular relation found in categorical data (e.g. good/average/poor knowledge with gender etc.) is statistically significant or not. For that purpose, p value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Altogether 340 students were made part of study from 17 years of age through 25 years while mean age was 21 years with standard deviation of 2.73. This includes 68 students from each of 5 years of MBBS. Number of female participants slightly outnumbered the male ones i.e. 50.5% (n=172) females while 49.5% (n=168) males. Majority of the respondents i.e. 57.4% (n=195) belonged to the age group 21-23 years, while 33.2% (n=113) were from 17-20 years age group and only few (9.1%; n=31) were 24 years and above in age. Economic categorization was also done and it was found that majority of the students (44.4%; n=151) were found to have per month family income within the range of Rs. 50,000 to 1 lac. The mean general knowledge score recorded is 15.39 while 4 and 22 are minimum & maximum scores respectively. About 54% (n=183) students had good general knowledge and this percentage was higher in females i.e. 65% (n=119; p=0.01). Table II (part a) shows that knowledge is more (53%; p=0.00) good in

third year students. Likewise, proportion of good knowledge was found to be greater (65%; p=0.7) in age group 24 years and above. Regarding production of vitamin D on ‘direct’ exposure to sunlight, 80% (n=274) participants tick marked the ‘yes’ column and majority (91%; p=0.00) were of final year. In nutritional knowledge, the mean score recorded was 5.16 whereas the maximum and minimum scores are 10 & 1 respectively. Only 47% (n=161) students had good nutritional knowledge. Table II (part b) shows that knowledge is better (65%; p=0.00) in second year students. Likewise, proportion of good knowledge was found to be greater (50%; p=0.7) in age group 24 years & above. Moreover, only 55% (n=186) participants were aware of the fact that fatty fishes are main dietary source of vitamin D and this percentage was highest (76%) in third year students (p=0.00).

Knowledge regarding vitamin D		Year of MBBS					Total
		First year	Second year	Third year	Fourth year	Final year	
a) General knowledge	Poor	0	10	2	0	0	12
	Average	26	29	30	34	26	145
	Good	42	29	36	34	42	183
Total		68	68	68	68	68	340
b) Nutritional knowledge	Poor	10	4	10	10	10	44
	Average	38	20	23	32	22	135
	Good	20	44	35	26	36	161
Total		68	68	68	68	68	340

Table II: Knowledge of Medical Students regarding Vitamin D

In this section, the mean score recorded was 42.41 while 27 & 60 are the minimum and maximum scores respectively. About 33 % (n=112) participants had good attitude with higher proportion in females (40%; p=0.01). Attitude was better (38%; p=0.67) in 24 years and above age group. Figure 1 shows that attitude was better (54%; p=0.00) in third year students. Only 23 % (n=78) participants ‘strongly agreed’ to the fact that insufficient education regarding usefulness of sun exposure, prevents adequate production of this

Figure I: Attitude with year of MBBS

vitamin. Alarming, just 16 % (n=55) participants 'strongly agreed' to the fact that use of sunscreens prevents sun exposure required for vitamin D production.

Only 8.8% (n=30) students had good practice and this percentage was higher in females (16%; p=0.00). Figure 2 shows that poor practice was more prevalent (38%; p=0.16) in first year students. Likewise, proportion of good practice was found to be greater (19%; p=0.04) in age group 24 years. Regarding direct exposure to sun, only 20 % (n=68) participants opted for 'always' (i.e. regularly). Moreover, only 6 % (n=20) participants 'always' consume fish twice weekly to keep themselves vitamin D sufficient. Regarding consumption of fortified milk, only 10 % (n=34) participants 'always' consumed it and this practice was more prevalent (11%; p=0.00) in those with income within Rs.50, 000 to 1 lac. Regarding intake of vitamin D supplements, 11 % (n=38) participants 'always' take them while 13 % (n=46) take them 'often'. Furthermore, 16 % (n=54) participants 'always' use sunscreens on face with greater proportion of users as females (23%; p=0.00).

Figure II: Practice with year of MBBS

Discussion

We document first Pakistani KAP survey to date, regarding vitamin D being done particularly on MBBS students, considering a public sector medical university as the setting of the study. Needless to mention, vitamin D is one of its kind particularly considering its mode of synthesis (via sun) as well as being dual(hormone/nutrient) in nature. Moreover, this vitamin has such functions in body that if present adequately has a major role in preventing a lot of morbidities¹³. Though most readily available via sunlight yet insufficiency of vitamin D is affecting about 50% of the population globally³. Deficiency of this vitamin is common in the New Zealand, Middle

East, United States, Asia, Europe and Australia³. Furthermore, hypovitaminosis D predominantly occurs in young, adolescents and old aged people^{14, 15}. Also, it is chiefly prevalent in people with colored complexion and those avoiding exposure to sun^{15, 16}.

In our study, only half of the students (53.8%) have good general knowledge which is a bit disappointing as the participants are medical students, the future forbearers of health in community. Almost half (47%) participants had good nutritional knowledge. Moreover, the nutritional knowledge was better (64.7%) in second year students probably because of the fact that they are currently studying biochemistry that improved their knowledge. These results are consistent with the study conducted in India on college students where a similar proportion of students knew about the sources of this vitamin¹. Logically, our results should have been more encouraging because the Indian study considered the intermediate students while our study included the medical students.

Despite good general and nutritional knowledge, only few (32.9%) participants had good attitude and this has significant relationship with female gender. Most probably this relationship is because females are more concerned about their health as compared to males. This relationship of attitude with gender was consistent with the Chinese study¹⁷. Similarly, there was a significant relationship of good attitude with third year class most likely because of the fact that they have just entered the clinical side and so they think more seriously about health issues.

Our study also shows the negative approach of participants regarding sun exposure as only 32% of them strongly agreed to the fact that urbanization is leading to decreased vitamin D by reducing sun exposure. Similarly, just a few strongly agreed to the fact that inefficient education regarding sun exposure benefits has reduced vitamin D production. Moreover, very few (16%) of them strongly agreed to the statement that sunscreens reduce the required exposure to sunlight for making sufficient amount of this vitamin. Such an inclination of the participants is highly disappointing as these participants are medical students.

Alarming, very few (8.8%) participants had good practice and this reflects extreme lack of motivation. Like attitude, practice is also better in females perhaps for the same reason as females are more concerned about health. Moreover, as the studies document that

deficiency is more prevalent and more severe in females so they might see doctor for the symptoms and so practice became better⁸. It is also seen that practice improved with age such that greater proportion of age group 24 years and above had good knowledge. Similarly, its relationship with per month family income is such that good practice is more prevalent (11.3%) in middle class family income (Rs. 50,000 to 1 lac) as good practicing also requires adequate nutritional intake of vitamin D which is obviously affected by the economic status. But since upper class family income also has poor practice then this is probably because with rise in economic status the dietary intake shifts to more junk foods and more sedentary life leading to reduced sun exposure.

In present study, just a few (20%) students have daily sun exposure and only 6% students consume fish regularly. Similarly, very few participants take fortified milk and vitamin D supplements to keep themselves vitamin D sufficient. Besides, almost a similar proportion of students do daily outdoors walk. When it comes to sunscreen use, more (10%) students use it on face and just 10% of them use it on hands. As expected, sunscreen use is more in females as they are always conscious of their skin color. Regarding practice our results are relatively more encouraging than results from China particularly with respect to the use of sunscreens.¹⁷ About 83% of students in Chinese study, used sunscreens. Reason behind this difference of results could be attributed to geographical, socioeconomic and educational factors. It is because apart from local sun brightness, sunscreen use also depends on its availability and affordability.

Conclusion

Findings obtained via this study depict the prevailing trends regarding general knowledge, nutritional knowledge as well as attitude and practices towards vitamin D in MBBS students. Despite being medical students, these trends were not up to that mark as it should be. Such results have dual threats and both of them cannot be ignored at any cost. Firstly, it definitely would be making those students deficient of vitamin D, particularly females. Secondly, medical students are harbinger of health to their country and so their inappropriate attitude towards such an important vitamin is risk to the entire nation. Thus, it becomes something which demands immediate and an effective action.

References

1. Arora H, Dixit V, Srivastava N. Evaluation of Knowledge, Practices Of Vitamin D And Attitude Toward Sunlight Among Indian Students. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2016;9(1):308-13
2. Masood SH, Iqbal MP. Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in South Asia. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2008 Oct 1; 24(6):891-7.
3. Holick MF. Vitamin D deficiency. *N Engl J Med.* 2007;357(3):266-81
4. Marwaha RK, Tandon N, Garg MK, Kanwar R, Narang A, Sastry A, et al. Vitamin D status in healthy Indians aged 50 years and above. *J Assoc Physicians India.* 2011; 59:706-9.
5. Hyppönen E, Läärä E, Reunanen A, Järvelin MR, Virtanen SM. Intake of vitamin D and risk of type 1 diabetes: a birth-cohort study. *The Lancet.* 2001 Nov 3;358(9292):1500-3.
6. H. Riaz, A.E. Finlayson, S. Bashir, S. Hussain, S. Mahmood, F. Malik & B. Godman. Prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency in Pakistan and implications for the future. *Expert Rev Clin Pharmacol.* 2016;9(2):329-38
7. Vu LH, van der Pols JC, Whiteman DC, Kimlin MG, Neale RE. Knowledge and attitudes about vitamin D and impact on sun protection practices among urban office workers in Brisbane, Australia. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2010 Jul 1; 19(7):1784-9.
8. Christie FT, Mason L. Knowledge, attitude and practice regarding vitamin D deficiency among female students in Saudi Arabia: a qualitative exploration. *Int. J. Rheum. Dis.* 2011 Aug 1; 14(3):22-9.
9. Burney WA, Fakhri HA, Fakhri M, Iffikhar R, Urooj A. Knowledge of doctors working in Karachi about Vitamin D. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2011 Apr-Jun; 27(2):357-60
10. Haq I, Tariq N, Afzal M, and Rajput AM. Vitamin D Deficiency and its Associated Factors amongst College Students. *JIMDC.* 2016;5(2):54-58
11. Deficiency—An Emerging Public Health Problem In Pakistan. *JUMD.* 2010 Jan-Jun. 1(1):4-9
12. Amiri P, Asghari G, Sadrosadat H, Karimi M, Amouzegar A, Mirmiran F, Azizi F. Psychometric properties of a developed questionnaire to assess knowledge, attitude and practice regarding vitamin D (D-KAP-38). *Nutrients.* 2017;9(5):471.
13. Kulie T, Groff A, Redmer J, Hounshell J, Schrage S. Vitamin D: an evidence-based review. *JABFM.* 2009 Nov 1;22(6):698-706.
14. Bakhtiyarova S, Lesnyak O, Kyznesova N, Blankenstein MA, Lips P. Vitamin D status among patients with hip fracture and elderly control subjects in Yekaterinburg, Russia. *Osteoporosis Int.* 2006 Mar 1;17(3):441-6.
15. Sedrani SH. Low 25-hydroxyvitamin D and normal serum calcium concentrations in Saudi Arabia: Riyadh region. *Ann Nutr Metab.* 1984;28(3):181-5.
16. Nesby-O'Dell S, Scanlon KS, Cogswell ME, Gillespie C, Hollis BW, Looker AC, Allen C, Dougherty C, Gunter EW, Bowman BA. Hypovitaminosis D prevalence and determinants among African American and white women of reproductive age: third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 1988–1994. *AJCN.* 2002 Jul 1;76(1):187-92.
17. Zhou M, Zhuang W, Yuan Y, Li Z, Cai Y. Investigation on vitamin D knowledge, attitude and practice of university students in Nanjing, China. *Public Health Nutr.* 2016 Jan;19(1):78-82.

Authors Contributions

Ruqayya Junaid: Literature review, introduction, methodology, data analysis, results and discussion, **Saadia Feroz:** Contributed in research proposal writing, data collection, analysis, and results, **Aashi Mughal:** Contribution in naming the article, sample size calculation and research methodology, data analysis, results and conclusions

How to Cite this Article: Junaid, R., Feroz, S., & Mughal, A. (2019). Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Medical Students Regarding Vitamin D. Journal of Rawalpindi Medical College, 23(S-2), 98-103